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Studying the Impact of Mulch Materials on the Physio-Morphological Characteristics of *Nitraria schoberi* L.

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Abstract:

Iran has lots of arid areas which the annual precipitation is low. Therefore, establishment of plants is hard. Therefore, at present study, the effectiveness of biological hydrogel (biological mulch or b), PLANTBAC vegetation layer (Pb), sand (sa), and barley straw (st) with rain harvesting techniques in micro-catchment scale (inter-row system) on plant characteristics of *Nitrariaschoberi* including establishment rate, fresh and dry biomass, etc. was tested. According to the results, plant height was significantly higher in the sand treatment than in other treatments. The dry yield of aerial parts indicated that all treatments showed a significant difference from the control. Leaf dry and fresh weight showed that both PLANTBAC treatment and sand were significantly more than the control. Root fresh and dry weight was significantly higher than the control on all four mulch treatments. According to the results, there is no significant difference between the environment (non-micro-catchment and micro-catchment) and the different treatments, so, we can propose each treatment by considering its price for the region. it can be concluded that some treatments had more effect on plant traits than the others, because of better absorbing adequate moisture and preparing nutrients for plants. Hence, they can be proposed for the region. Thus, concerning the effectiveness of present mulches on a variety of plant properties, the price of each, availability, and condition of the area, they can be used to establish plants in desert areas and restore these areas by controlling dust and dunes movement, soil erosion, etc.

Keywords:

Nitrariaschoberi, amendments, physio-morphologic characteristics, deserts, Semnan.

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Introduction

Iran has a hot and dry climate and the annual precipitation is low. In addition to the lack of rainfall, temporal and spatial distribution is also very poor (Kianian, 2022, 2019; GanjiKhorramdel, 2018; Yang et al., 2018). Soils in these areas have not been developed and have low organic matter and in most cases are alkaline. The plants of these areas are resistant to drought and salinity and their growth form is mostly as shrub and bush (Luo et al., 2022; Ahmadi, 2019; Shilev, 2020; Ahmadi and Saeidi, 2018; Azimi et al., 2018). Reducing desertification and rehabilitation of degraded areas is needed to reclaim and maintain the vegetation in these areas. In addition, the vegetation increases productivity and stability against the risk of erosion and reduces salinity (El-Sheikh *et al.*, 2010). Also, the plants have an industrial value, forage, conservation (soil and reduce erosion), scenic beauty, etc. (Javaid et al., 2022; Ashraf *et al.*, 2018; Hasanporiet *al.*, 2020; Wang, 2009, Wang, 2011 and Kabiri, 2015; Benabderrahim et al., 2018). One of the most important and most usable development and regeneration methods of vegetation is planted. But the lack of precipitation, high evapotranspiration, and inappropriate rainy season leads to destroying seedlings, especially in the critical period of establishment and projects failure of planting in arid areas (Kianian, 2022). Also, high implementation costs and provide the water needed for irrigation at the beginning of the planting period is a very serious obstacle to the development of the cultivated area. It has been reported that hydrogel networks improve aeration and drainage (Bearce, McCollum, 1977), reduce plant water stress (Teameet *al.*, 2017; Liet *al.*, 2018; AbediKuhpai, and Sohrab, 2004; Gehring, Lewis, 1980; Li et al., 2017), and improve seed coating (Pamuk, 2004). Wallace and Wallace (1986) stated that the most favorable results for the emergence of the seed and water penetration are obtained of an anionic polymer and cationic polymer was less effective. In addition, appropriate amendments affect the antioxidant defense mechanisms (El-Metwally et al., 2021; Benabderrahim *et al.*, 2018; Cordeiro *et al.*, 2011; Song et al., 2019). Hydrogels have been used for the establishment of seedlings and transplanted trees in arid areas of Africa and Australia to increase plant survival (Alharb, 2015; Specht, Harvey-Jones 2000; Save 1995; Callaghan *et al.* 1988, 1989). Specht, Harvey-Jones (2000) found that less tolerant tree species to drought reacted more favorably to the use of hydrogels. When the hydrogels in the bed of growth were placed total dry weight *brayleana Flindersia* (maple Queensland) and *muelleri Dysoxylum* (red beans) increased, while species resistant to drought *Flindersia australis* (teak Australia) and *Grevillea robusta* (oak silk) did not show a significant increase in total dry weight. In an experiment, irrigation was stopped six days, so all the control seedlings were destroyed, but the survival rate of modified soils with hydrogel was 57% and 71% (Iqbal et al., 2022; Charles *et al.*, 2017; Callaghan *et al.*, 1989; AbediKuhpai, and Sohrab, 2004). Drought-sensitive plants such as *Petunia parviflora* (Atlas), reacted well to the hydrogel in arid conditions, and the dry weight and flowers number increased (Shilev, 2020; Boartright *et al.*, 1997).

Arikiriza *et al.*, (2009), seedlings of 9 species of *Eucalyptus grandis*, *Eucalyptus citriodora*, *Pinus caribaea*, *Araucaria cunninghamii*, *Meliavolkensii*, *Grevillea robusta*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Maesopsis eminii* and *Terminalia superba* planted into the pots filled with five types of soil sandy, sandy loam, loam, silt loam and clay with two levels of 2.0 and 4.0 w% enriched hydrogels. Pots kept in the greenhouse and under non-stress conditions and the amount of biomass based on dry weight and according to root, stem, leaf, and twig were measured. After eight weeks the plants were harvested and measured. The results showed a significant difference in root dry weight of the seedlings planted in soil containing hydrogel at 8 species of plants compared to control, and the dry weight of stem, leaf, and twig all of the species have given a significant increase compared with the control. Hydrogel used in different textures of the soil in this study had different results. For example, both levels in sandy soil in addition to having difference with the control, showed a difference together and 4.0% was better, but there was no significant increase in biomass in sandy loam soil with an

increase of hydrogel from 2.0 to 4.0 percent. The plant species also have different reactions. *Eucalyptus citriodora* unlike other species in both the hydrogel had similar production in the loamy soil and the *Meliavolkensii* with increasing hydrogel reacted to a reduction in root dry weight. Reduction in root dry weight by increasing the amount of hydrogel in the heavier soils is repeated in several other plant species, which may be due to the ease of access to water and no need for further development of the plant root system (Silva et al., 2020). Final increase of production 9 species with the use of hydrogel from 150 to 220 percent compared to the control was assessed. To reveal the relationship between the increase in available water and plant growth, the increase in available water of the two types of sandy loam and sandy clay soils was measured 3.2 and 1.8 times, respectively, compared to the control, but despite this very significant difference, the difference in crop production in these two types of soil was only 16% (Verma et al., 2018; Kader et al., 2017; Sharma and Bhardwaj, 2017; Rashid et al., 2019).

Materials and methods

Study Area

The study was carried out by planting seedlings for 2 years in the Natural Resources Research Station of Semnan (the station is part of the typical desert area of Semnan and has a large extent (Figure 1). The average rainfall is 109.3mm, the evaporation rate, 2582.3 mm, the number of sunshine hours, 3134.5 hours, the average annual temperature, 18°C, the minimum moisture content, 23%, and the number of frost days is 19 days. Maximum rainfall occurs in winter in this region. The city is classified in an arid and cold climate based on the Domarten method.

The plant and its properties

-*Nitrariaschoberi*

Nitrariaschoberi is the plant that treatments are tested on. Therefore, to introduce *Nitrariaschoberi*, some properties of this plant is given below. *Nitrariaschoberi* is of *Nitraria* gender and *Zygothylaceae* family with five species as *schoberi*, *reyusa*, *sibirica*, *sphaerocarpa* and *komaroui* (Kianian, 2022; Mojiri, 2011). Only, *Nitrariaschoberi* species is native to Iran. This plant is woody and highly branched and has rough and thorny branches (Figure 2). Its inflorescence is as tail-scorpion pistil with white color and usually will appear in late April.

Figure 1. Map of the study area.

Its fruit is a drupe colored brown to black, containing a seed that is visible in late June. Leaves are fleshy and stems are sharp and woody at the end. The most important values of *Nitrariaschoberi*

includes the role of conservation (dunes stabilization and prevention of soil erosion), use the fruits in the biological synthesis of gold and silver nanoparticles, forage production value, industrial value, especially in the dyeing, softening the air, refuge, wildlife, landscape beauty, and medicinal value. medicinal value includes 18 alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds and 2 pseudo-serotonins, organic acids, antioxidants, etc. (Sharifi-Radet *al.*, 2016, 2015, 2.14) In the case of reproducing it must be said that, so far, have experienced several methods, including direct sowing (seeding and hill drop planting), cuttings and seedling production in plastic pots, which the best method is to produce pot seedlings.

Figure 2. *Nitrariaschoberi* plant in the site

-Amendments materials and mechanisms of their action

One of the best and newest methods in further savings in water consumption is to use of PLANTBAC panel and biological hydrogels. The following explanations are given about them.

-PLANTBAC

Components forming the product contain albumin biopolymers, water, minerals, and recyclable herbal elements. Its life is 5 to 8 years. By adding natural nutrients, restores the soil and prohibits soil erosion by water and wind. Release and absorption of essential nutrients are the direct effects of this layer. In desert combating, the spread of vegetation could be done quickly due to keeping the soil moisture.

-Biological hydrogel

Biological absorbent moisture materials used in the study are a mixture of microbial and plant polymers, which about 40% by weight have water-absorbing properties and, unlike super-absorbents prevents salt accumulation in the root zone due to less water absorption. Its pH is 0.5 ± 7 and has no salt. 90% germination index tests showno hydrogel phytotoxic effects on plants. This as a carrier of used microorganisms in the soil (fertilizer or biological poison) leads to increase soil biological activity. Dry areas make some Mucilage properties around the roots that prevent stress to the plant.

-Research Methodology

In the method, the seeds are planted in plastic pots in the nursery of Hasanabd station, Damghan, and then the seedlings are transferred to Semnan research station. Then, the seedlings were planted in the form of a split-plot design with a randomized complete block base with 3 replications and 10 observations in the first week of December 2021. The first irrigation was performed simultaneously with planting seedlings. The treatments are as follows:

- Rainwater harvesting technique at two levels (technique application, non-technique application).
- Mulch and moisture-absorbent materials in five levels (biological hydrogel or biological mulch), PLANTBAC, sand, straw, and control treatment)

In the location of the project, in the Natural Resources Research Station of Semnan' Agriculture and Natural Resources Research Center, it was drilled 150 holes to the diameter and depth of 50 cm and the treatments were placed in each repetition. The pits' distance from each side was 3 m. In the sand treatment, sand (diameter 2 to 5 mm) with a thickness of 5 cm was placed in the canopy of the plant. For barley straw treatment was acted the same and some straw to a thickness of 5 cm was placed in the canopy of the plant. For biological hydrogel, at first 140 liters of water in a barrel of 220L was heated until 80°C and 40 ml of concentrated hydrogel was shed into it to be thinner. Then, 2 Liter is shed in the soil under the plant and 1 Liter in the soil next to the seedling. For treatment of PLANTBAC, at first, one number was halved and two halves were placed to a short distance from each other at the hole (one half in the bottom and then another above it). Finally, the seedlings were planted. For applying the technique of rainwater harvesting according to the area condition (slope, climatic factors, soil depth, etc.) was used inter-row systems were treated for all repetitions until its effect on plant growth be determined. The irrigation time of the seedlings was in summer during 4 irrigations (15 June, 15 July, 15 August, and 15 September) in the first year.

The volume of water for irrigation in all treatments was based on reaching humidity to the control plant wilting point and the amount of water needed to reach to field capacity level in the control plant. Finally, due to the volume of water consumption (constant against control) for treatments and the resulting biomass in each treatment, water use efficiency (WUE) and the efficiency of the technique were determined. In the end, sampling of soil factors was conducted according to the relevant instructions. Then, the samples were transferred to laboratories and they were prepared, and then each one was measured according to the relevant guidelines by using devices or methods.

In the third year, characteristics of survival percentage (establishment), biomass rate, growth rate (leaf area and height), as well as fresh and dry weight of roots and shoots and dry shoot yield according to relevant methods (meter, balance, etc.) were measured in the field and laboratory.

To analyze the data, first, the normality of experimental errors was performed by Shapirovilk, Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Kramer van Misses, and Anderson Darling tests for each trait (Table 1). The results showed that the experimental errors were normal. The experiment was performed as a split-plot design in a randomized complete block design with three replications. In this way, the environmental factor at two levels (non-micro-catchment and micro-catchment) and the mulching factor at five levels (control, PLANTBAC vegetation layer, biological hydrogel, straw, and sand) are considered as independent variables and traits as dependent variables in the experiment. Then, analysis was performed using SAS software version 9.1.3. Mean comparisons were performed using LSD test if. Pearson correlation was also performed for correlation between different traits. The results for each trait are given below.

Results and discussion

Analysis of characteristics of the plant such as survival (establishment), biomass, growth rate, and aerial dry yield are provided in table 1. Given that the treatments PLANTBAC and bio- hydrogel were done for the first time in Iran and the world, thus, there aren't cases for comparison with the other researches results, but some research done on the two other treatments, i.e., sand and straw on other species, which are discussed below.

Table 1. Analysis of variance split-plot in a randomized complete block design

Sources of Changes	Degree of freedom	Squares mean						
		Percent of establishment	Root fresh weight	Root dry weight	Plant height	Aerial dry yield	Fresh biomass weight	Dry biomass weight
Block	2	7.5 ns	5.126 ns	12.871 ns	9.052 ns	3.319 ns	26.562 ns	568.859 ns
Environment	1	7.5 ns	0.55 ns	0.166 ns	11.685 ns	2.449 ns	884.315 ns	1442.425 ns
The first error	2	158.611	10.31	5.709	3.224	3.731	666.767	937.203
Mulch	4	27.917 ns	516.382**	368.127**	134.113**	35.677**	14923.744**	3138.792*
Mulch× Environment	4	8.657 ns	8.318 ns	11.966 ns	4.082 ns	0.531 ns	526.949 ns	931.77 ns
Experimental error	16	12.454	24.853	14.953	2.333	0.461	695.867	870.987
CV (%)		3.91	11.58	12.73	4.65	5.59	10.54	19.84

* and ** significant at a confidence level of 5%, and 1%, respectively.

Continue Table 1. Analysis of variance split-plot in a randomized complete block design

Sources of Changes	Degree of freedom	Squares mean				
		Stem fresh weight	Stem dry weight	Leaf fresh weight	Leaf dry weight	Leaf area of a plant
Block	2	39.804 ns	82.294 ns	67.012 ns	705.41 ns	155464.366 ns
Environment	1	163.835 ns	111.828 ns	294.897 ns	855.546 ns	173415.05 ns
The first error	2	257.403	380.738	166.852	381.087	378293.637
Mulch	4	3908.65**	2653.422**	2412.441**	347.575**	1872475.755**
Mulch× Environment	4	327.436 ns	231.184 ns	65.495 ns	7.059 ns	40296.546 ns
Experimental error	16	288.862	226.623	152.177	37.091	87381.84
CV (%)		15.9	18.64	12.29	15.17	22.34

- Percentage of plant establishment

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed the effect of any of the sources of variance analysis table wasn't significant ($P < 0.05$) (Table 1). So, it can be concluded that there was no significant difference between the environment and the different treatments in terms of the average percentage of the establishment. Pearson correlation analysis between the percentage of plant establishment with other measured characteristics of the soil and the plant showed that the percentage of plants establishment with electrical conductivity and pH had a moderate negative correlation ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$). With water use efficiency, plant dry weight and moisture content had a moderate positive correlation ($0.4 < r < 0.6$). The results of Orikiran *et al.*, (2009), Silva *et al.* (2020) and Sharma and Bhardwaj (2017) indicated a significant and positive impact of super-absorbent on the establishment and aerials biomass of nine species of trees. According to Li *et al.*, (2004) and Song *et al.* (2019), the effects of stabilization of sand and restore the species diversity cryptogam and soil fertility in the desert, Tengger, north China, showed that re-vegetation leads to improve the environmental conditions and thus the establishment and release of cryptogams on the dunes Tengger. Padilla *et al.*, (2009) in a study as the selection of species in revitalizing arid brush-lands concluded that the highest amount of survival was for legumes and followed by leafless species and brushes C_4 , attributes that are considered to maximize the use of resources in cleared areas and unfertilized, while reducing the waste of water. Therefore, the selection of species with middle sequence along these features must be considered for successful restoration. Esmaeilpour (2012) and Silva *et al.* (2020) in a study entitled effect of super-absorbent polymer and mycorrhizal inoculation on the establishment of seedlings several species, showed that they have a great impact on the establishment of seedlings.

- Plant height

The results of experimental error normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1). Results mean comparison the effect of mulch on height showed that plant height was significantly higher than other treatments in the sand treatment (GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, 2018). Straw treatments, biological hydrogel, and PLANTBAC also had not significantly different in terms of plant height from the controls (Figure 3). Pearson correlation analysis between plant height and other characteristics of the soil and plant showed that the average height of the plant with the pH had a moderate negative correlation ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$) and a moderate positive correlation ($0.4 < r < 0.6$) with aerial dry weight and dry and fresh weight a plant. A strong positive correlation ($0.6 < r < 0.8$) with the water use efficiency and a very strong positive correlation with aerial dry yield ($0.8 < r$). Results Gush *et al.*, (2006), Benabderrahim *et al.* (2018) and Verma *et al.* (2018) and Benabderrahim *et al.* (2018) as the effect of polyethylene mulch and straw mulch, showed that mulch of straw (wheat or rice) improved the plant height as compared to control (Song *et al.*, 2019).

- Dry yield of aerial parts

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1). A comparison of the average effect of mulch on yield of aerial dry indicated that all treatments showed a significant difference to the control (Benabderrahim *et al.*, 2018; Song *et al.*, 2019). The highest yield of aerial dry was obtained in the sand treatment and the lowest in the straw treatment after the control (Figure 4). Pearson correlation analysis between leaf area of a plant with other measured characteristics of the soil and the plant showed that the leaf area of a plant had moderate negative correlation ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$) with the EC and sodium. The weak positive correlation ($0.2 < r < 0.4$) with the percentage of establishment and weak negative correlation ($-0.2 < r < -0.4$) with the sodium adsorption ratio. Aerial dry yield positively was correlated to the organic matter of root, leaf area and fresh weight of a plant, leaf dry weight, aerial fresh weight, fresh biomass weight, storage, and sequestration carbon and soil organic matter, aerial dry yield, and leaf fresh weight ($0.4 < r < 0.6$). With a plant dry weight, aerial dry weight, and the percentage of mycorrhizal had a strong positive correlation ($0.6 < r < 0.8$) and a strong negative correlation ($-0.8 < r$) with pH. The water use efficiency and height had a very strong positive correlation ($0.8 < r$). Results Gush *et al.*, (2006), Silva *et al.* (2020), El-Metwally *et al.* (2021) as the effect of polyethylene mulch and straw mulch showed that mulch of straw (wheat or rice) have improved the stem and pod yield as compared to the control.

Figure 3. Effect of different treatments on height

Figure 4. Effect of different treatments on aerial dry yield

- Fresh biomass weight

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1). A comparison of the average effect of mulch on fresh biomass weight showed there was a significant difference in the two PLANTBAC and sand treatment plants to the control (El-Metwally et al., 2021; Orikiriza et al., 2009, Azimi, 2018; GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, 2018; Kianian, 2019). The results also showed that both treatment bio- hydrogel and straw were not significantly different from control. The highest fresh biomass weight belonged to PLANTBAC (Figure 5). Pearson correlation analysis between fresh biomass weight with the other measured characteristics of the soil and the plant showed that fresh biomass weight has a moderate negative correlation ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$) with sodium adsorption ratio, the amount of sodium, and pH. It had a weak negative correlation ($-0.2 < r < -0.4$) with wsc. With sequestration, storage, and soil organic carbon, the average total organic matters aerial, root organic matters, magnesium, mycorrhizal percent, dry weight a plant and fresh weight of root, aerial dry yield, and leaf dry weight positive had a moderate positive correlation ($0.4 < r < 0.6$). With a fresh and dry weight of aerial, leaf fresh weight had a very strong positive correlation ($-0.8 < r$) and a strong positive correlation ($0.6 < r < 0.8$) with the area of the plant leaf (Benabderrahim et al., 2018; Song et al., 2019).

- Dry biomass weight

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.05$) (Table 1). A comparison of the average effect of mulch on the weight of dry biomass showed that only PLANTBAC treatment showed a significant difference with the control (Silva et al., 2020; Azimi, 2018; Orikiriza et al., 2009, GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, 2018; Kianian, 2019; El-Metwally et al., 2021). The results also showed that three treatments, sand, straw, and bio-hydrogel had no significant difference with the control. The greatest amount of dry biomass weight belonged to the PLANTBAC treatment (Figure 6). Pearson correlation analysis between dry biomass weight was with other measured characteristics of the soil and the plant showed that the weight of dry biomass with bulk density, electrical conductivity, sodium adsorption ratio, the amount of sodium, and pH has a moderate negative correlation ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$). Also, the fresh weight leaves a weak positive correlation ($0.2 < r < 0.4$). with the fresh weight of leaf, forage ash, dry weight and organic matters of the root, soil organic carbon, the percentage of mycorrhizal, dry and fresh weight of stem, magnesium, average total organic matter

of aerial, dry weight of leaf, leaf area a plant, DMD and fresh biomass weight had moderate positive correlation ($0.4 < r < 0.6$) (Song et al., 2019).

Figure 5. Effect of different treatments on fresh biomass weight.

Figure 6. The effect of different treatments on dry biomass weight.

- Root fresh weight

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1). A comparison of the average effect of mulch on the root fresh weight showed that the root fresh weight was significantly higher than the control on all four mulch treatments (Silva et al., 2020; El-Metwally et al., 2021; Orikirizaet al., 2009, Azimi, 2018; GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, 2018; Kianian, 2019). The results also showed that the highest fresh weight was related to PLANTBAC that was differed from straw and sand treatment in terms of root fresh weight (Figure 7). Pearson correlation analysis between the fresh weight of the root with characteristics measured in the soil and plant showed that the fresh weight of root with calcium and sodium, pH, SAR, and bulk density has a moderate negative correlation ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$), with an average total organic material of plant, organic materials of the root, leaf area of a plant, sequestration, storage, organic carbon and soil organic matters, carbon sequestration total plants, the percentage of mycorrhizal, fresh biomass weight, calcium, magnesium a moderate positive correlation ($0.4 < r < 0.6$). With leaf organic matters, moisture content, plant carbon,

nitrogen, and carbon storage of the plant, a strong positive correlation ($0.6 < r < 0.8$), with the root dry weight a very strong positive correlation ($0.8 < r$) and a strong negative correlation with litter organic matters ($-0.8 < r$) (Song et al. 2019).

- Root dry weight

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1). Mean comparison of the effect of mulch on the root dry weight showed that root dry weight was significantly higher than the control in all treatment groups (Song et al. 2019; El-Metwally et al., 2021; Orikirizaet al., 2009, Azimi, 2018; GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, 2018; Kianian, 2019). The results also showed that the highest dry weight was related to PLANTBAC that was differed from straw and sand treatment in terms of root dry weight (Fig. 8). Pearson correlation analysis between root dry weight with other characteristics in the soil and plant showed that root dry weight with calcium and sodium and bulk density had a moderate negative correlation ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$), with an average total organic material of plant, root organic materials, leaf area of a plant, sequestration, storage and soil organic matters, carbon sequestration total plant, mycorrhizal percent, dry biomass weight, calcium, magnesium, a moderate positive ($0.4 < r < 0.6$). Also, with leaf organic matters, moisture content, plant carbon, nitrogen, and carbon storage of total plant, a strong positive correlation ($0.6 < r < 0.8$), with the dry weight of the root a very strong positive correlation ($0.8 < r$) and a strong negative correlation with litter organic materials ($-0.8 < r$) (Silva et al., 2020).

Figure 7. The effect of different treatments on root fresh weight.

Figure 8. Effect of different treatments on root dry weight

- Stem fresh weight

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1). A comparison of the average effect of mulch on shoot fresh weight showed that the two treatments PLANTBAC and sand had the greatest shoot fresh weight and had a significant difference with the control (El-Metwally et al., 2021; Orikirizaet al., 2009, Azimi, 2018; GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, 2018; Kianian, 2019; AbediKuhpai, and Sohrab, 2004). Also, results showed that the two treatments straw and bio-hydrogel had no significant difference in terms of the dry weight of the shoot (Figure 9). Pearson correlation analysis between shoot fresh weight with other characteristics in the soil and plant showed that shoot fresh weight with SAR, sodium, and pH had a moderate negative correlation ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$) and with the storage and carbon sequestration in soil and root organic matters a weak positive correlation ($0.2 < r < 0.4$). With the water use efficiency, average total organic materials of plant, mycorrhizal percent, dry biomass weight and shoot dry yield had a moderate positive correlation ($0.4 < r < 0.6$). The leaf area of a plant has a strong positive correlation ($0.6 < r < 0.8$), with the leaf fresh weight, shoot dry weight, and fresh biomass weight a very strong positive correlation ($0.8 < r$) (Song et al. 2019; Silva et al., 2020).

- Stem dry weight

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1). Mean comparison of the effects of mulch on shoot dry weight showed that sand treatments and PLANTBAC have the highest dry weight and had a significant difference with the control (Song et al. 2019; Orikirizaet al., 2009, Azimi, 2018; GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, El-Metwally et al., 2021; 2018; Kianian, 2019). The results also showed that both straw treatment and bio-hydrogel had no significant difference in terms of shoot dry weight with the controls (Fig. 10). Pearson correlation analysis showed a moderate negative correlation between shoot fresh weight with potassium, SAR, sodium, and pH ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$). Also, it showed a moderate positive correlation with phosphorus, water use efficiency, root organic materials, plant's height, average total organic materials of plant, mycorrhizal percent, the weight of dry biomass, and leaf dry weight ($0.4 < r < 0.6$). With plant leaf area and shoot, the dry yield had a strong positive correlation ($0.6 < r < 0.8$), with the fresh weight of leaf, stem fresh weight, and biomass fresh biomass weight a very strong positive correlation ($0.8 < r$) (Silva et al., 2020).

Figure 9. The effect of different treatments on stem fresh weight.

Figure 10. Effect of different treatments on stem dry weight.

- Leaf fresh weight

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1). Mean comparison of the effect of mulch on leaf fresh weight showed that both beek plant treatment and sand were significantly more than the control. While the bio-hydrogel treatment and straw were not significantly different from the control (Orikirizaet *al.*, 2009, Azimi, 2018; GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, 2018; Kianian, 2019; El-Metwally et al., 2021). The maximum weight of the leaf fresh was observed in the PLANTBAC (Figure 11). Pearson correlation analysis between the fresh weight of leaves and other characteristics measured in the soil and plant showed that leaf fresh weight with an average total organic material of plant, leaf dry weight, average total organic materials of the shoot, stem organic materials, and leaf area a plant had a moderate positive correlation ($0.4 < r < 0.6$), with a fresh and dry weight of stem and fresh biomass weight any plant a very strong positive correlation ($0.8 < r$). Also, it showed a weak positive correlation with the weight of dry biomass ($0.2 < r < 0.4$) and a moderate negative correlation with the WSC ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$) (Song et al. 2019).

- Leaf dry weight

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1). Mean comparison of the effect of the mulch on dry weight showed that two PLANTBAC treatments and sand were significantly more than the control (Teame et al., 2017; Orikirizaet *al.*, 2009, Azimi, 2018; GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, 2018; Kianian, 2019). While the bio-hydrogel treatment and straw were not significantly different from the control. Maximum leaf dry weight was observed in the PLANTBAC treatment (Figure 12). Correlation analysis between leaf dry weight with other characteristics of the soil and the plant showed that leaf dry weight with shoot dry yield, fresh and dry weight of shoot, water use efficiency, dry weight of a plant, the percentage of mycorrhizal, fresh and dry biomass weight a plant, leaf fresh weight, alkaloid, DMD and moisture content had a moderate positive correlation ($0.4 < r < 0.6$), a strong positive correlation with the leaf area of a plant, ($0.8 < r$). Also, it showed a moderate negative correlation with sodium, pH, electrical conductivity, percent sand, zinc, bulk density, and sodium adsorption ratio ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$).

Figure 11. Effect of different treatments on fresh weight of leaf.

Figure 12. Effect of different treatments on leaf dry weight

- Leaf area of a plant

The results of experimental errors normality by all four tests confirmed the data normality. Analysis of variance showed that the effect of mulch was significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 1) (Teame et al., 2017; Orikirizaet al., 2009, Azimi, 2018 and Kianian, 2019). A comparison of the average effect of mulch on the area of plant leaves showed there was a significant difference in three PLANTBAC treatments, sand, and bio-hydrogel with the control (GanjiKhorramdel, and Keykhaee, 2018; El-Metwally et al., 2021; AbediKuhpai, and Sohrab, 2004). Results also showed that the leaf area of a plant had no significant difference in the straw treatments. Most of the leaf area per plant was obtained in the PLANTBAC treatment (Figure 13). Pearson correlation analysis between leaf area of a plant with other measured characteristics of the soil and the plant showed that the leaf area of a plant was negatively correlated with bulk density, sodium adsorption ratio, the amount of sodium, and pH ($-0.4 < r < -0.6$). With magnesium had a weak positive correlation ($0.2 < r < 0.4$) and to the organic matters leaves, water use efficiency, DMD, mycorrhizal percent, the weight of dry biomass a plant and fresh and dry weight root, storage and sequestration carbon, soil organic carbon, shoot dry yield and leaf fresh weight a moderate positive correlation ($0.4 < r < 0.6$). Also, the fresh and dry weight of stem, leaf dry weight, and fresh biomass had a strong positive correlation ($0.6 < r < 0.8$) (Silva et al., 2020).

Figure 13. Effect of different treatments on a leaf area.

Conclusion

The process of desertification and soil degradation leads to pollution and the tremendous waste of water resources, soil, and plant. Also, water resources and poor chemical and physical characteristics of the soil are the most important factor limiting the establishment and growth of plant species in arid and desert areas. Given that, oil mulches in our country and some other countries have environmental impacts and high transportation costs, they can be replaced with new materials and compatible with nature with less cost. Therefore, we can use super-absorbents and amendments, which can improve the success rate of seedling establishment and water use efficiency. In this study, we studied the effectiveness of bio-hydrogel (biological mulch), the herbaceous layer of PLANTBAC, sand, and barley straw along with rainwater harvesting techniques in the micro-catchment scale (inter-row system) on some characteristics of desert plant *Nitraria schoberi* including percentage survival (establishment), biomass, growth rate (leaf area and height), phenolic compounds and the alkaloid of total plant and fresh and dry weight of roots and aerals and aerals dry yield in treatments and various iterations.

Based on the analysis results of the effect of mulch on phenol, alkaloid, and the percentage of plant establishment, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the environment and the different treatments in terms of the amount of phenol, i.e., we can propose each treatment concerning the price for the region. For plant height, plant height in the sand treatment was significantly higher than in other treatments. This suggests that the treatment than other factors is better to preserve moisture in the soil for plants. Straw treatments, biological hydrogel, and PLANTBAC also had no significant difference in plant height with the control. According to the results of the effect of the mulch on aerial dry yield, treatment groups had no significant difference from the control. The highest yield of aerial dry was in the sand treatment and the lowest in the straw after the control treatment. According to the analysis of the effect of mulch on a leaf area, it can be concluded that the three treatments PLANTBAC, sand, and bio-hydrogel had a significant difference from the control. Results also showed that the leaf area of the plant had no significant difference in the straw treatment. Most of the leaf area per plant was achieved in the treatment PLANTBAC, which can be proposed for the region. Then sand and bio-hydrogel are recommended.

Results of the effect of mulch on fresh biomass weight showed that the treatment PLANTBAC and sand had a significant difference with the control. The results also showed that both straw treatment and bio-hydrogel were not significantly different from the control. The highest fresh biomass weight

belonged to the PLANTBAC, which can be proposed for the region. Then sand is recommended. Results of the effect of mulch on dry biomass weight showed that the only PLANTBAC treatment has a significant difference from the control. The results also showed that three treatments, sand, straw, and bio-hydrogel had no significant difference with the control in terms of dry biomass weight. The greatest amount of dry biomass weight belonged to the PLANTBAC treatment, it is probably due to the absorption of more moisture in the soil and the presence of its nutrients which absorb by plants. Hence, they can be proposed for the region. According to the analysis of the effect of mulch on the fresh and dry weight of root, it can be concluded that all four treatments were significantly higher than the control. The results also showed that the highest fresh weight and dry of the root was related to the treatment PLANTBAC, which had a difference with the straw treatment and sand in terms of fresh weight and dry of the root, it is probably due to the absorption of more moisture in the soil and the presence its nutrients which absorb by the plant. Hence, it can be proposed for the region. According to the analysis of the effect of mulch on the fresh and dry weight of stem, it can be concluded that two PLANTBAC and sand had the highest fresh weight and dry of stem and had a significant difference with the control. The results also showed that both straw treatment and bio-hydrogel had no significant difference with the control in terms of fresh weight and dry of the stem. This shows that the two treatments are better than other treatments in absorbing adequate moisture and food (due to a higher concentration of nutrient and water uptake). Hence, they can be proposed for the region. Results of the effect of mulch on fresh weight and dry of leaf showed that two PLANTBAC treatments and sand were significantly more than the control. While both treatments straw and bio-hydrogel had no significant difference with the control in terms of fresh weight and dry of the leaf. Maximum leaf dry weight was observed in the PLANTBAC treatment. This shows that the two treatments are better than other treatments in absorbing adequate moisture and food (due to a higher concentration of nutrient and water uptake). Hence, they can be proposed for the region. Thus, concerning the effectiveness of the effects of mulches present on a variety of factors, soil, and soil moisture and the price of each, availability and terms of area, they can be used to establish plants in desert areas and by controlling dust and dunes, soil erosion, etc. the areas are restored.

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